

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING STRING INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE IN THE DIRECTION OF MUSIC EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of the teacher and the importance of his professional competence in the process of training competitive, creative thinking and highly professional specialists in the conditions of the modern education system. At the same time, the issues of developing independent thinking, creative thinking and practical skills in students through innovative pedagogical technologies, problem-based learning and teacher-student traditions in the educational process are scientifically analyzed. In particular, the effectiveness of pedagogical approaches aimed at increasing the creative activity of students is substantiated on the example of art education.

The progressive development of society and the growing demand for highly qualified specialists in various fields pose new and responsible tasks for the education system. Especially in the context of globalization processes and the rapid development of digital technologies, the quality of education, teaching methods and professional skills of teaching staff are becoming decisive factors. The training of a new generation of specialists for all fields is closely related, first of all, to the training of teaching staff with deep theoretical knowledge, high professional potential and the ability to think creatively. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, on May 30, 2019 “On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21, 2020 [2], “On measures to further increasing the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD-4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” of April 21, 2020, No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” of April 20, 2021, Decree No. PD-6208 of. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

In particular, in the field of art education, the development of independent thinking, creative approach and practical skills of students is one of the most important pedagogical

tasks. Therefore, the implementation of modern, problem-based and creative teaching methods in the educational process, the involvement of students in the active learning process are of great importance. This legal document provided for the development and approval of the Regulation “On the Museum Treasures Fund of Uzbekistan” and the Instruction “On the Procedure for Registration, Collection and Storage of Historical and Cultural Treasures Stored in Museums” [4].

As we know, the effectiveness of training a new generation of specialists in all fields depends, first of all, on the training of teaching staff who have thoroughly mastered the relevant disciplines, have sufficient professional knowledge and practical skills. A teacher should strive to develop his creative and scientific potential, improve his professional skills, be an example with his personal behavior, and be able to direct the worldview and creative direction of young people towards success through the ability to find the right solutions in various situations.

In today's era of rapid development of technology and information technologies, ample opportunities and conditions have been created for young people to become fully mature. This serves to shape them as inquisitive, initiative and active specialists. The system of continuing education performs a very responsible and multifaceted task in educating the future generation. Only an experienced, highly qualified and pedagogically skilled teacher can effectively fulfill such a task.

Today, young people who are studying are required to deeply master all subjects, have a broad outlook, be spiritually mature people, know foreign languages, and be able to effectively use information and communication technologies.[5] In order to train competitive personnel, the teacher himself must have high professional experience and skills. In the educational process, the teacher-student relationship between teachers and students plays an important role in the exchange of experience and achieving professional development. The effectiveness of teaching is ensured by introducing various teaching forms and methods based on the characteristics of the subject and specialty. Modern teaching technologies serve to strengthen the knowledge and abilities of students through the tasks they are given, and to open up new opportunities.

Through these methods, the activity of students in the process of higher education increases, they thoroughly prepare for training sessions, their mental thinking is formed, and their abilities develop. Today's students are increasingly interested in creative activity, independent thinking, and expressing their desires and aspirations.

The teacher's teaching method is based on science, it should be directed to solving problems through discussions, developing the student's independent activity and creative ability. Through this, the purposeful mastering of learning outcomes is achieved.[6]

One of the main requirements is that students should think independently, analyze existing problems and develop their activities in the field of art education. It is necessary for the student to understand the importance of such an approach, to pay serious attention to the formation of knowledge and thinking.

In the process of teaching specialized subjects, students should be taught to use the acquired knowledge and skills to independently solve the difficulties and shortcomings,

overcome obstacles and draw conclusions. This creates the basis for the development of independent thinking and reasoning in them.

Therefore, the educational process should be organized in such a way that the student can draw independent conclusions in the process of analyzing the work and the ability to think creatively is formed in it. The more works a student performs independently during his educational activities, expresses his opinion during the performance process, and approaches the study of the work responsibly, the faster and more effectively he will master the material.

It should be noted that lessons based on discussions are of great importance in developing students' independent thinking skills, forming a broad worldview and analytical thinking.[7]

In general, specialists increase their knowledge potential by analyzing educational materials in a problematic way, solving them with evidence, and consciously mastering knowledge. Students are also required to understand problematic situations, look for ways to solve them, and draw scientifically and logically based conclusions.

The main goals of lessons in art education are:

1. Mastering new knowledge and skills;
2. Creative mastery and application of knowledge in practice;
3. Development of creative activity and abilities.

If interest in the subject wanes during art education, it is necessary to arouse interest in students, revitalize their educational activities, pose intellectual and practical questions, teach them to analyze works, and provide practical assistance in solving problems.

To organize effective education, it is necessary to form a research approach to solving educational and professional problems in future art specialists. As a result, the effective use of teaching methods develops the intellectual and practical activity of students, expands the possibilities of independent research and creative thinking.

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